

PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF STUDENTS' MASTERY OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN AGRICULTURAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. *In this article, we have chosen several ways to define a set of pedagogical conditions. They are as follows: determining the requirements of educational documents in terms of the existing problem; It is written about identifying the specific characteristics of students in the process of developing their communicative competence.*

Keywords: *document, professional activity, specialist, education, program, communicative, person-oriented.*

From the point of view of pedagogy, it is a set of objective possibilities, content, form, method and pedagogical methods aimed at solving the set tasks.

A.Budnik, N.A.Kobzeva, I.N.Korzennikova, Ye.V.Smirnova, O.A.Karpovich and other scientists were engaged in the development of pedagogical conditions for the organization of education. According to scientists, to develop students' independence, motivation to learn; to improve the specialist's professional activity; Pedagogical conditions aimed at developing educational goals and content aimed at developing personal professional qualities of students are the most effective.

In our research, we relied on the definition of scientist O.A.Karpovich. According to his definition, pedagogical conditions are a set of measures that ensure that students achieve the necessary knowledge, skills and qualifications during the educational process. O.A.Karpovich's conclusion that to consider the set of pedagogical conditions as a dynamic, flexible system, and to get rid of the use of secondary, random and scattered conditions, a critical attitude to the conditions included in this system is required.

For this reason, within the framework of our research, we need to determine the necessary and sufficient conditions for the pedagogical foundations of improving organizational culture among students of the Agrarian Higher Education Institution.

We chose several ways to determine the set of pedagogical conditions. They are as follows: determining the requirements of educational documents in terms of the existing problem; to determine the specific characteristics of students in the process of developing their communicative competence.

As a result of this, a set of conditions was determined, which are as follows: the educational process is based on a personal-praxisological approach; the development of professional self-awareness of learners ensures their personal approach to the process of communicative activity; communicative relations between the teacher and the student are established on the basis of collaborative creativity. We will cover these conditions in more detail and thereby determine the influence of the model on successful implementation in practice in the process of developing communicative competence. One of the main conditions - the educational process in education is

built on the basis of a personal-praxisological approach - implies that the creation and implementation of the educational process in terms of the development of communicative competence will give a positive result and a high level of efficiency.

Understanding the positive results and effectiveness of pedagogical activity, developing the image of the student "I", the need to develop the individual pedagogical creativity of the pedagogue in the process of professional activity shows the relevance of using a personal-praxeological approach to teaching.

In recent times, works of a methodological nature have been created, which discuss the problems of personalized education in sufficient detail. Based on the rules of the concept of the educational process aimed at the individual, the student is considered as a process of self-realization as a creative subject.

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Therefore, the main task of modern education is to develop the personality of the student. According to V.P.Zinchenko, the person-oriented approach can be considered the main principle of modern pedagogy, which can be called "pedagogy of cultural communication".

The core of the person-oriented approach is the theory of personality development (personal development) developed in the works of V. I. Grachev, L. K. Geikhman and other scientists. The main idea of this theory is to develop the student's activity and independence, to consider him as an active subject of his activity and to develop his ability to manage himself and realize his opportunities, abilities and potential.

A person-oriented approach to education makes the education of a creative and emotional emotional-value-based attitude to the world (universe) the most important priority. Proponents of this approach (M.V.Klarin, L.K.Geichman, A.V.Mudrik, T.S. Serova, T.G.Dementeva, etc.) rely on personal qualities such as a person's orientation, the direction of his valuable bases, his plans in life, and the dominant motives of his activity. understood as

According to Z.D.Rasulova, a person-oriented approach - taking into account the student's thinking and action strategy, directs the development of his personality, characteristics and abilities. This means that the educational environment should be adapted to the student's abilities. According to him, the educational environment, pedagogical conditions, educational and upbringing process fully realize the student's personal potential, develop his abilities, ensure that he matures as a person, and enrich his thinking and worldview. A unique aspect of the person-oriented approach is to recognize the personality of the learner, to create a comfortable and necessary environment for his comprehensive development. in educational processes, this type of education serves to educate students such qualities as independence, creativity, initiative, responsibility, as well as independent, creative and critical thinking skills.

During our research, we focused on the important aspects of using electronic textbooks and the Internet in agricultural education based on information technologies.

Work on establishing an electronic government has also been started in Uzbekistan. According to the existing practice of the world experience, it consists of two interconnected, but functionally independent parts, the Government Internet and the external infrastructure. The government Internet covers the internal infrastructure of the information system, which is used by state structures in mutual relations in the implementation of state corporate tasks. External infrastructure covers public information infrastructure that enables the government to interact with citizens (G2C) and organizations (G2B).

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the "Electronic Government" system development center under the Ministry of Information Technologies and Communications Development was established based on the government's decision (PM No. 250 of September 16, 2013). The ultimate goal of introducing Electronic Government in Uzbekistan is:

- it is the creation of a perfect state management electronic apparatus:
- Wide range of interactive services;
 - delivery and clarity of activity reports of government bodies;
 - easy access to services and privacy;
 - active participation and awareness of citizens in political processes;
 - free exchange of information;
 - creation of favorable conditions for the provision of public services for the population and business activities;
 - to support the expansion of citizens' self-service opportunities;
 - is to increase the opportunities of all voters to participate in governance processes and state administration.

Information and communication technologies have been introduced in our country for several years to purposefully provide interactive state services to citizens and legal entities through the websites of state bodies and the Government portal of the Republic of Uzbekistan. At the Government meeting on January 18, 2013, dedicated to the results of the socio-economic development of the country in 2012 and the most important priorities of the economic program of 2013, the First President Islam Karimov noted the importance of developing the concept and comprehensive program of the "Electronic Government" system in the country.

Korean and other foreign experts are actively involved in the development of projects, roundtable discussions, meetings, seminars and meetings are held with experts from various ministries and departments of Uzbekistan in this direction. As a result of the introduction of the "Electronic Government" system, it is expected to transition to fully transactional services, which excludes the participation of citizens and business representatives in the use of public services and direct communication with public servants. This, in turn, serves to create additional conveniences for residents and improve business conditions.

The mobile version of the Government portal (m.gov.uz) was developed in order to attract mobile Internet users. This version contains the most important and useful information for the population. Also, mobile applications of the government portal were developed on Android and Windows mobile platforms in order to provide the population with operational information about the events taking place in our country.

The Government portal of the Republic of Uzbekistan supports the functional process and order of the activities of the state authorities and forms part of the electronic infrastructure system of the state authorities and management bodies. As an implementation of the decision of the

Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 378 of December 30, 2012 "On measures to further improve the activity of the Government portal of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the Internet, taking into account the provision of interactive public services", A single interactive public services portal was created and launched on the Internet on July 1, 2013. The purpose of this information resource is to create wide opportunities for users, and first of all, business entities, to obtain information about public services and to provide public services on the basis of the "one-stop shop" principle.

Currently, the Single Portal provides the following opportunities:

- obtaining information about state bodies and services;
- filling out the application and other documents necessary for obtaining state services in electronic form;
- sending an application for public service;
- receiving information about the process of reviewing an application for public service;
- obtaining the results of public services;
- registration and hakazo of business entities.

Today, more than 300 state institutions and organizations are connected to the single portal, and more than 150 state services are provided through the portal. The UZINFOCOM center provides expert advice on issues of development and implementation of ICT in public administration and the following areas of the Single portal for the responsible employees of state bodies: interaction of state bodies with the Single portal, introduction of interactive services and their use in the Single portal integrate with;

Entering information about the services provided by state bodies on the Unified Portal and filling in information about state bodies that are generally used and shared;

Interaction of state bodies with the Government portal (www.gov.uz), as well as cooperation regarding the information provided for posting on the Government portal;

It is a service that allows users registered from www.id.uz to be identified on various sites and information resources that support OpenID technology through ID.UZ system logins and passwords. For site owners (external systems), ID.UZ is :

- The ability to freely connect to the system in order to ensure that your users pass authorization through their account in the ID.UZ system;
- There is no need to spend time and money on processes such as creating a list of users, organizing their registration, restoring data and checking their accuracy;
- Authentication of users in different ways, taking into account different security requirements;
- The fact that users have different statuses, taking into account the different requirements for the data to be in their original form;
- The use of a unique identifier of users allows to create interaction between different information systems.

For users, ID.UZ is: - You don't need to register on many sites and remember different logins and passwords; As soon as you change your personal information in one system, this information will automatically change in all the systems you use; High level of security and reliability: recovery of your data in different ways, possibility to verify the correctness of the data through several steps, safe storage of personal data in a single place, possibility to view and analyze the history of actions; Provides access to e-Government systems, including the Unified Interactive

Services Portal. The ID.UZ system allows you to transfer authorization not only to the projects of the UZINFOCOM Center, but also to all sites that support OpenID technology. Among them: Gov.uz Lex.uz., natlib.uz WWW.UZ; Ziyonet.uz Utube.uz; Fikr.uz Desk.uz; cctld.uz Gazeta.uz and other sites that support OpenID technology.

Figure 2.1.1. Access to a single interactive services portal

In March 2012, the Center established and put into operation the Portal of Communal Management and Housing Fund on the Internet.

It can be viewed at www.e-kommunal.uz, www.kommunal.uz and www.ek.uz. This portal serves to control the activities of organizations providing communal services by the public, to provide consumers with interactive services in the communal sector, and to make payments for communal services. This portal allows citizens to quickly apply to organizations and state bodies operating in the communal sector, as well as to monitor the implementation of the measures taken on the submitted applications. If the measures taken on the appeal do not satisfy the user of the portal, the portal allows to see the history of the appeal - that is, it can present the results of the measures taken since the date of the appeal to the control bodies. In addition, one of the main tasks of the portal is to increase utility bills on time through the online system and to check the status of the bill of payments.

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